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Adversity and Emotional Quotients of Catholic School Teachers in Relation to Work Performance: Basis for Enhancement

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Abstract

This study examines the relationship between adversity quotient (AQ), emotional quotient (EQ), and work performance among Catholic school teachers in the Diocese of Kabankalan. Employing a descriptive-quantitative research design, the study surveyed 185 junior and senior high school teachers from 17 diocesan schools. Stratified random sampling was used to ensure representation across demographics. Data were collected through standardized instruments for AQ, EQ, and work performance. Statistical analyses, including ANOVA and chi-square tests, were applied to determine significant differences and relationships among variables. Findings indicate that Catholic school teachers generally possess high levels of AQ and EQ, with work performance rated as proficient. No significant differences were observed in AQ and EQ when grouped according to age, sex, length of service, employment status, gross monthly income, or faculty designation. However, work performance significantly varied based on age, length of service, employment status, and income level, with more experienced and higher-earning teachers exhibiting better performance. Notably, AQ and EQ were found to be significantly related, while neither AQ nor EQ demonstrated a significant correlation with work performance. The study suggests that administrators should consider teacher demographics in performance assessments and provide professional development programs to enhance AQ and EQ. Additionally, mental health initiatives and training on resilience and emotional intelligence may further support teacher well-being and efficiency. Future research could expand the scope by including additional variables and a broader population to enhance understanding of factors influencing teacher performance.

Keywords: *adversity quotient, emotional quotient, work performance, catholic school teachers, resilience, emotional intelligence*

Introduction

Adversity quotient, as defined by Stoltz (1997) and cited by Tindoc (2019), is the study of how well people cope with adversity and difficulties. This explains why some people handle difficult circumstances better than others.

As such, teachers are heavily exposed to the demands of efficiency, capabilities, and competencies in the execution of complex tasks in this rapidly expanding environment. They will inevitably run into pressures, complexities, and adversities while juggling these responsibilities which could either be some type of school, community or personal challenges.

In addition, Tindoc (2019) pointed out that emotional intelligence is not just about being kind, putting on a good act, and letting sentiments run free; it also has nothing to do with exploitation, control, or manipulation of others (Cherniss & Adler, 2000). As such, the ability to effectively perceive and comprehend one's own and other people's emotional reactions is the essence of emotional intelligence (Cherniss & Adler, 2000).

The researcher as priest administrator believed that it is vital to consider the adversity and emotional quotients of teachers with regards to their work performance in order to keep a life-work balance.

Research Questions

The purpose of the study was to determine the relationship of adversity quotient, emotional quotient and work performance of Catholic Schools Teachers in the Diocese of Kabankalan. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of Catholic School Teachers in the Diocese of Kabankalan in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. length of service;
 - 1.4. employment status;
 - 1.5. gross monthly income; and
 - 1.6. faculty designation?
2. What is the Adversity Quotient of Catholic School Teachers in the Diocese of Kabankalan?
3. What is the Emotional Quotient of Catholic School Teachers in The Diocese of Kabankalan?
4. What is the Work Performance of the Catholic Teachers in the Diocese of Kabankalan?
5. Is there a significant difference in the Adversity Quotient when taken as a whole and when grouped according to profile?
6. Is there a significant difference in the Emotional Quotient when taken as a whole and grouped according to profile?
7. Is there a significant difference in the work performance of Catholic School Teachers in the Diocese of Kabankalan when

taken as a whole and when grouped according to profile?

8. Is there a significant relationship between the Adversity Quotient and Emotional Quotient of Catholic Teachers in the Diocese of Kabankalan?
9. Is there a significant relationship between the Adversity Quotient and Work Performance of Catholic Schools Teachers in the Diocese of Kabankalan?
10. Is there a significant relationship Emotional Quotient and Work Performance of Catholic School Teachers in the Diocese of Kabankalan?

Methodology

Research Design

The research design used in this study is descriptive–quantitative as it aims to “describe, explain, and validate findings” relating to adversity quotient, emotional quotients, and work performance of catholic school teachers in the Diocese of Kabankalan.

“Descriptive studies have an important role in educational research. They have greatly increased our knowledge about what happens in schools” (Association of Educational Communication Technology, 2011).

Moreover, Ardales (2008) explained that descriptive is intended to study “what is.” It is a research design appropriate for studies that aim to discover the phenomenon's condition or relationships. It is characterized by an attempt to gather, analyze, interpret, and report the status of certain phenomena, such as a social institution, group, or area. It is a fact-finding procedure concerned with conditions that are held, processes that are going on, or trends that are developing.

Ardales further explained that descriptive research design finds procedures, particularly on existing conditions and relationships, the prevailing practices, beliefs that are held, effects that are felt, and developing trends.

Similarly, according to John W. Best, descriptive research design is most appropriate in behavioral science. It deals with relationships with variables, the testing of hypotheses, and developing generalizations, theories, or principles that have universal validity. It is also concerned with the functional relationship and involves events that have already occurred and may be related to a present condition or situation. (Research in Education, John Best p.25, 104-125)

Respondents

The subjects and respondents of this study were the junior and senior high school catholic teachers in the Diocese of Kabankalan for the academic year 2022 - 2023. Both teachers from junior and senior high schools which were chosen randomly participated in the data gathering.

There is a total of eighteen (17) catholic schools that is owned by the Diocese of Kabankalan namely; Cabarrus Catholic College, Inc., Holy Rosary Academy of Sipalay, Negros Occidental, Inc., Ilog Catholic High School, Inc., Immaculate Conception Academy of Dancalan, Inc., Kabankalan Catholic College, Inc., Magballo Catholic High School, Inc., Nuestra Senora de las Nieves, Inc., Our Lady of Lourdes High School of Candoni, Inc., Our Lady of Sorrows Academy, Inc., San Blas Academy, Inc., San Isidro Academy of Moises Padilla, Negros Occidental, Inc., San Ramon Catholic School, Inc., St. Columbans Academy of Cauayan, Negros Occidental, Inc., St. Joseph High School, Inayauan, Cauayan, Neg. Occ., Inc., St. Michael's Academy of Hinobaan, Inc. St. Vincent's High School, Inc. and Stella Maris Academy of Himamaylan, Inc. All junior and senior high school teachers will be utilized as respondents of the study. A total population will be used; thus, sample size will no longer be computed.

Stratified random sampling was utilized in this study. Stratified random sampling is a type of probability sampling using which a research organization can branch off the entire population into multiple non-overlapping, homogeneous groups (strata) and randomly choose final members from the various strata for research which reduces cost and improves efficiency. Members in each of these groups should be distinct so that every member of all groups gets an equal opportunity to be selected using simple probability. This sampling method is also called “random quota sampling”. Fleetwood, (2022).

With the help of a statistician a sample size was taken from the total population. Table 1 below shows the distribution of the population and sample size of the respondents.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Name of Schools</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample size</i>
School A	6	3
School B	19	10
School C	14	8
School D	19	10
School E	52	28
School F	13	7
School G	14	8
School H	17	9

School I	14	8
School J	12	6
School K	27	15
School L	24	13
School M	28	15
School N	16	9
School O	25	13
School P	20	11
School Q	22	12
Total	342	185

Table 1 above shows the distribution of the respondents of this study after the stratified sampling technique. Among the seventeen (17) catholic schools that is owned by the Diocese of Kabankalan, there are 3 from School A, 10 from School B, 8 from School C, 10 from School D, 28 from School E, 7 from School F, 8 from School G, 9 from School H, 8 from School I, 6 from School J, 15 from School K, 13 from School L, 15 from School M, 9 from School N, 13 from School O, 11 from School P and 12 from School Q. A total of 185 samples as respondents which was taken from the population.

Instrument

The data gathering instruments such as Adversity Quotient and Emotional Quotients used in this study are adopted from Nissa Marie Tindoc's 2019 study, Emotional and Adversity Quotients of Science Teachers in Relation to Work Performance.

The work performance evaluation tool however is owned by the Department of Education, Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers. The aforementioned instrument is adopted and utilized by the Commission on Education of the Diocese of Kabankalan.

The Adversity and Emotional Quotients questionnaire was divided into three (3) different parts. Part I was composed of the respondents' demographic profile, including age, sex, length of service, employment status, gross monthly income and junior or senior high school faculty.

Part II of the questionnaire was composed of questions on the Emotional Quotient of teachers. The mean score is the quotient of the categories in the adopted survey questionnaire. Interpretations include Very High Level, High Level, Moderate Level, Low Level and Very Low were assigned to range of mean scores, 4.21 – 5.00, 3.41 – 4.20, 2.61 – 3.40, 1.81 – 2.60, and 1.01 – 1.80, respectively.

Part III of the questionnaire included questions regarding Adversity Quotient of teachers. The scale shows the interpretation of the mean scores obtained. 4.21 – 5.00 Very High Adversity Quotient, 3.41 – 4.20 High Adversity Quotient, 2.61 – 3.40 Average Adversity Quotient, 1.81 – 2.60 Low Adversity Quotient, and 1.01 – 1.80 Very Low Adversity Quotient.

In assessing the Work Performance of the respondents, a standardized Performance Evaluation tool utilized by the Diocesan Commission of Education was used. Originally as mentioned above the Work Performance questionnaire is own by the Department of Education, Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers. Below is the scale for interpretation of the data acquired.

Procedure

The researcher asked the permission of the Bishop to conduct the study. Upon approval, the commission on education of the aforementioned diocese was notified. A letter to inform the principals and school heads was sent to set the data gathering.

The researcher personally performed the survey and the orientation of the teacher respondents to know the results first hand. The three (3) component surveys on adversity and emotional quotient were given to teacher responders. The respondents were informed of the study's objectives and received detailed instructions on how to complete the questionnaires. They were also asked for permission to use their assessment form or work performance rating. Also, respondents received assurances regarding the privacy of the findings.

After the data had been collected, authorization from the school officials was requested in order to evaluate the teachers' Work Performance Ratings. Data were then handled with extreme care and secrecy. A statistician evaluated the results statistically as part of the handling of the data.

Data Analysis

Research is said to be empirical in the sense that it uses concrete and appropriate tool to treat the data.

This study made used the Measure of Central Tendency specifically the Mean to identify the instructors' profile, ANOVA was used to treat the significant difference, and to see the relationship of phenomena Chi-Square was utilized.

To answer statement problems number 1, 2, 3, and 4 which is the profile of Catholic School Teachers in the Diocese of Kabankalan in terms of, sex, age, length of service, employment status, gross monthly income and faculty designation. Second the Adversity Quotient third the Emotional and fourth the Work Performance of the Catholic Teachers in the Diocese of Kabankalan? A measure of central tendency, specifically weighted mean was used.

A single number that describes how a set of data congregates around a central value is known as a measure of central tendency. It is a means to characterize the middle of a data set, to put it another way. The mean, the median, and the mode are the three central tendency measures.

The "mean" is the "average" you're used to, where you add up all the numbers and then divide by the number of numbers. To answer statement problem no. 5, 6, and 7 if there a significant difference in the Adversity Quotient, Emotional

Quotient and Work Performance when taken as a whole and when grouped according to profile? ANOVA was utilized. ANOVA partitions the observed variance into different components to conduct various significance tests. ANOVA is applied to a set of data containing one independent variable and examines whether a linear relationship exists between a dependent variable and an independent variable (Neukrug and Fawcett, 2010).

To answer statement problem no. 8, which states, Is there a significant relationship between adversity quotient emotional quotient of Catholic School Teachers in the Diocese of Kabankalan? Chi-square was used.

To answer statement problem no. 9 and 10, which states, Is there a significant relationship between adversity quotient emotional quotient and work performance of Catholic School Teachers in the Diocese of Kabankalan? Chi-square was also used.

The Chi Square distribution is the distribution of the sum of squared standard normal deviates. The degrees of freedom of the distribution is equal to the number of standard normal deviates being summed. Therefore, Chi Square with one degree of freedom, written as $\chi^2(1)$, is simply the distribution of a single normal deviate squared. A Chi Square calculator can be used to find that the probability of a Chi Square (with 2 df) being six or higher is 0.050. (Lane.D, 2010). Below is the formula for Chi-square.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis and interpretation of data that were gathered to provide answers to the statement of the problems and analyze related topics to give clarity to the study.

Frequency and Percent Distribution in the Profile of Teachers

The table below shows the Frequency and Percent distribution in the Profile of Catholic Teachers in terms of Age, Sex, Length of Service, Employment Status, Gross Monthly Income and Faculty Designation.

Table 2. *Frequency and Percent Distribution in the Profile of Catholic School Teachers*

<i>Profile</i>	<i>Classification</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Age	20-30 years old	124	67.03
	31-40 years old	35	18.92
	41-50 years old	15	8.11
	51-60 years old	10	5.41
	above 60 years old	1	3.60
Sexccc	Male	64	34.59
	Female	121	65.41
Length of Service	5 years & below	129	69.73
	6-10 years	28	15.14
	11-15 years	14	7.57
	16 years & above	14	7.57
Employment Status	Permanent	104	56.22
	Probationary	81	43.78
Gross Monthly Income	P10,000 & below	8	4.32
	P10,001-P15,000	134	72.43
	P15,001 & above	43	23.24
High School Faculty	Junior High School	109	58.92
	Senior High School	76	41.08

Table 2 presents that out of 185 respondents, there were 124 teachers, or 67.03%, who were aged 20-30 years old, 35 or 18.92%, were aged 31-40 years old, 15 or 8.11% were aged 41-50 years old, 10 or 5.41% were aged 51-60 years old, and 1 or 3.60% was aged above 60 years old. When it comes to their gender, a total of 64, or 34.59%, were male teachers, and 121, or 65.41%, were female. This suggests that educational institutions are now populated with a younger workforce and that the female gender is likely to be in the educational field.

When grouped according to the respondents' length of service, 129 teachers, or 69.73%, have worked for five years and below; 28, or 15.14%, have worked for 6-10 years; 14 or 7.57% have worked for 11-15 years, and 14 or 7.57% have worked for 16 years and above. Furthermore, there were 104 teachers, or 56.22%, who have permanent employment status, while 81, or 43.78%, are still probationary.

The gross monthly income of 8 teachers, or 4.32% of teachers, was P10,000 below, 134 teachers, or 72.23% of teachers, have an

income of P10,0001-P15,000, and 43 teachers, or 23.24% of teachers, have an income of P15,001 and above.

Also, out of 185 respondents, 109 or 58.92% were teaching in Junior High School and 76 or 41.08% were teaching in Senior High School.

Frequency and Mean of the Adversity Quotient of Catholic School Teachers

The table below presents the Adversity Quotient of Catholic School Teachers in the Diocese of Kabankalan.

Table 3. *Level of Adversity Quotient of Teachers in terms of frequency and mean*

<i>Level of Adversity Quotient</i>	<i>f</i>
Very high	13
High	98
Moderate	73
Low	1
Very low	0
Total	185
Mean	3.55
Interpretation	High

Out of 185 teachers, 13 were identified to have a Very High level of adversity quotient, 98 showed a high level, and 73 had a Moderate level.

The total mean for the Level of Adversity Quotient was 3.55, interpreted as High. The result shows that the Adversity Quotient of teachers in the Diocese of Kabankalan is significantly High.

This is profoundly related to the study conducted by Mwivanda (2016). It was discovered that secondary school instructors, tasked with implementing the curriculum and looking after the students under them, appear to bear the brunt of the majority of issues in educational institutions. Her research has also demonstrated that a person's ability to use adversity to their advantage can be called adversity quotient. The way a teacher handles hardship in their own life, in general, is most likely to influence how his or her students handle hardship and, as a result, impact the student's academic achievement.

Additionally, AQ has generated a great deal of scholarly attention in education. Investigated its purpose and how it affected the effectiveness of educators, particularly administrators, school principals (Williams, 2008), and specialists who taught special curricula (Santos, 2012).

Frequency and Mean of the Emotional Quotient of Catholic School Teachers

The table on the following page presents the Emotional Quotient of Catholic School Teachers in the Diocese of Kabankalan in terms of frequency and mean.

Table 4. *Level of Emotional Quotient of teachers in terms of Frequency and mean*

<i>Level of Emotional Quotient</i>	<i>f</i>
Very high	73
High	99
Average	13
Low	0
Very low	0
Total	185
Mean	4.07
Interpretation	High

When it comes to the teacher's Level of Emotional Quotient, 73 showed a Very High level, 99 showed a High level, and 13 showed a Low level.

The total mean for the said quotient is 4.07 which was interpreted as High. This result shows that the emotional quotient of the teachers in the Diocese of Kabankalan is notably high.

Thus, teachers that are emotionally intelligent are better able to handle challenging situations when their decisions may have an impact on the learning and wellbeing of the pupils. Additionally, it aids them in overcoming fresh difficulties brought on by unruly student groupings, overcrowded classrooms, or a lack of enthusiasm. It is possible to list a few qualities of an emotionally competent teacher. Such a teacher expends a lot of effort to foster a supportive environment in the classroom and considers the feelings of the students. He or she should be an adept listener who also pays attention to the demands of the students. An excellent teacher is characterized by a passion for teaching, dedication to students, and a distinct professional philosophy that enables them to build harmonious relationships with their students. Naturally, interpersonal skills are important, and characteristics like empathy, approachability, and treating kids

fairly can be addressed (Mortiboys, 2005).

Frequency and Mean of the Work Performance of Catholic School Teachers in the Diocese of Kabankalan

The table on the next page shows the frequency and percentage of Work Performance of Catholic School Teachers in the Diocese of Kabankalan for Academic Year 2022-2023.

Table 5. *Frequency and Percentage in the Level of Work Performance of Catholic School Teachers in the Diocese of Kabankalan for Academic Year 2022-2023*

<i>Level of Work Performance</i>	<i>F</i>
Outstanding	1
Very Satisfactory	138
Satisfactory	44
Unsatisfactory	1
Poor	1
Total	185
Mean	3.25
Interpretation	Proficient

The table above showed that only 1 teacher had an Outstanding level of work performance, 138 teachers were shown to have Very Satisfactory level and 44 were Satisfactory. On the other hand, 1 teacher had an Unsatisfactory level and 1 also had Poor level.

The total mean for the Level of Work Performance was 3.25 which was interpreted as Proficient. This result therefore shows that the Catholic School teachers in the Diocese of Kabankalan are competent and skilled when it comes to their field.

As such, through the mediation of the quality of working life, high-performance work systems have a direct and indirect impact on teachers' in-role performance and extracurricular behavior. The relationship between high-performance work systems and employees' work behaviors is mediated by their quality of working life (Shen, et.al., 2014).

Difference in the Level of Adversity Quotient of teachers when group in terms of Age

The table on the following page shows the difference of Adversity Quotient of catholic school teachers in terms of Age.

Table 6. *Difference in Adversity Quotient of teachers when grouped according to age*

<i>Age</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Mean</i>
20-30 years old	124	3.54
31-40 years old	35	3.57
41-50 years old	15	3.57
51-60 years old	10	3.71
above 60 years old	1	3.60

Computed value (F) = 0.37
P-value = 0.831
Decision = Accept Ho
Interpretation = Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Based on the table above, 124 teachers aged 20-30 years old had a mean adversity quotient of 3.54, 35 teachers aged 31-40 years old had a mean adversity quotient of 3.57, 15 teachers aged 41-50 years old had a mean adversity quotient of 3.57, 10 teachers aged 51-60 years old had a mean adversity quotient of 3.71, and 1 teacher aged above 60 years old had a mean adversity quotient of 3.60.

Upon using the Analysis of Variance, the computed value of 0.37 was obtained, which is below the P-value of 0.831 at a 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted. This means that there is no significant difference in teachers' adversity quotient level when grouped in terms of age. As such, the age of the Catholic School teachers in the Diocese of Kabankalan does not necessarily affect their level of adversity quotient.

Compared to Shen's research, this is the inverse (2014). Shen emphasized the importance of seniority and age in AQ. On the other hand, the findings of Sanchez's 2018 study revealed that respondents' Adversity Quotient was unaffected by their age.

Difference in the Level of Adversity Quotient of Teachers when grouped in terms of Sex

The table below shows the difference in the Adversity Quotient of catholic school teachers in terms of Sex.

Table 7. *Difference in the Level of Adversity Quotient of teachers when grouped according to Sex*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Mean</i>
Male	64	3.52
Female	121	3.57

Computed value (t) = -0.77

P-value = 0.441
Decision = Accept Ho
Interpretation = Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Based on the table, 64 male teachers had a mean score of 3.52, and 121 female teachers had a mean score of 3.57.

Upon using the Analysis of Variance, the computed value of -0.77 was obtained, which is below the P-value of 0.441 at a 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted. This means that there is no significant difference in teachers' adversity quotient level when grouped according to their sex. As such, the sex of the said teachers does not necessarily affect their adversity quotient level.

This aligns with a study by Sanchez (2018) that found that respondents' gender had no bearing on their Adversity Quotient. This is in line with the findings of a study conducted by Cura and Gozum (2011) among PLMCET sophomore students. The researchers found no appreciable gender-based differences in the respondents' Adversity Quotient. This shows that both respondents are equally capable of overcoming obstacles in life, regardless of their sexual orientation.

Furthermore, in their study, "Relationship Between Adversity Quotient and Academic Well-being Among Malaysian Undergraduates," Khairani and Abdullah (2018) used the independent sample T-test, one-way ANOVA, Pearson correlation, and linear regression. The study's findings revealed no differences in the mean AQ score between males and females.

Difference in the Level of Adversity Quotient of teachers when group in terms Length of Service

The table below on the next page shows the difference in the Adversity Quotient of catholic school teachers in terms of Length of Service.

Table 8. Difference in Adversity Quotient of teachers when grouped according to Length of service

<i>Length of Service</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Mean</i>
5 years & below	129	3.54
6-10 years	28	3.53
11-15 years	14	3.61
16 years & above	14	3.69

Computed value (F) = 0.56
P-value = 0.640
Decision = Accept Ho
Interpretation = Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Out of 185 respondents, 129 teachers who were in the service for five years and below had a mean score of 3.54, 28 teachers with 6-10 years in service had a mean score of 3.53, 14 teachers who were in the service for 11-15 years had a mean score of 3.61, and 14 teachers who were in the service for 16 years and above had a mean score of 3.69.

Upon using the Analysis of Variance, the computed value of 0.56 was obtained, which is below the tabular value of 0.640 at a 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted. This means that there is no significant difference in teachers' adversity quotient level when grouped according to the length of service. As such, the respondents' service length does not affect their AQ.

This is in contrast to a study by Bautista (2015), who discovered that faculty members' performance as teachers is "extremely satisfying" and their adversity quotient is "high." She also learned from the findings that faculty members' adversity quotients differed significantly depending on their academic level and length of service. When faculty members were grouped by age, academic rank, and duration of service, there was also a sizable difference in their ability to teach.

Difference in the Level of Adversity Quotient of teachers when group in terms Employment Status

The table shows the difference in the Adversity Quotient of Catholic School Teachers in terms of Employment Status.

Table 9. Difference in Adversity Quotient of teachers when grouped according to Employment Status

<i>Employment Status</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Mean</i>
Permanent	104	3.57
Probationary	81	3.54

Computed value (t) = 0.55
P-value = 0.584
Decision = Accept Ho
Interpretation = Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Out of 185 teachers, 104 with permanent employment status had a mean score of 3.57, while 81 who are probationary had a mean score of 3.54.

Upon using Analysis of Variance, the computed value of 0.55 was obtained, which is below the P-value of 0.584 at a 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted. This means that there is no significant difference in teachers' adversity quotient level when grouped according to employment status. It can be concluded that the respondents' employment status does not necessarily affect their AQ.

Employability is the collection of skills one possesses that increases their chances of choosing and obtaining a job where one will be happy and successful (Pool & Sewell, 2007). According to Hogan, Chamorro-Premuzic, and Kaiser (2013), an individual's high drive, willingness to work hard, and battling spirit, or what is referred to as the adversity quotient, are some of the factors that can affect employability. Businesses need their employees to have high adversity quotients in prosperous and challenging economic times.

Difference in the Level of Adversity Quotient of teachers when grouped in terms Gross Monthly Income

The table below shows the difference in the Adversity Quotient of catholic school teachers in terms of Gross Monthly Income.

Table 10. *Difference in the Level Adversity Quotient of teachers when grouped according to Gross Monthly Income*

Gross Monthly Income	F	Mean
P10,000 & below	8	3.31
P10,001-P15,000	134	3.54
P15,001 & above	43	3.65

Computed value (F) = 2.33

P-value = 0.100

Decision = Accept H_0

Interpretation = Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

In identifying the difference in adversity quotient in terms of monthly income, teachers earning P10,000 & below had a frequency of 8 with a mean score of 3.31, teachers earning P10,001-P15,000 had a frequency of 134 with a mean score of 3.54, and teachers earning P15,001 & below had a frequency of 43 with a mean score of 3.65.

Upon using Analysis of Variance, the computed value of 2.33 was obtained above the P-value of 0.100. Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted at a 0.05 level of significance. This means that there is no significant difference in teachers' adversity quotient level when grouped according to gross monthly income.

This implies that teachers' adversity quotients are not always influenced by their monthly pay. Similar findings from other studies about the motivational power of money were reached (Bergmann & Scarpello, 2002). They confirmed that when employees execute their jobs successfully, receiving this kind of reward is essential and greatly impacts their performance.

Difference in the Level of Adversity Quotient of teachers when grouped in terms Faculty Designation

The table below shows the difference in Adversity Quotient of catholic school teachers in terms of High School Designation.

Table 11. *Difference in Adversity Quotient of teachers when grouped according to Faculty Designation*

Faculty Designation	F	Mean
Junior High School	109	3.52
Senior High School	76	3.60

Computed value (t) = -1.20

P-value = 0.233

Decision = Accept H_0

Interpretation = Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

In the difference in adversity quotient when grouped according to High School Faculty, 109 Junior High School teachers had a mean score of 3.52, and 76 Senior High School teachers had a mean score of 3.60.

Upon using Analysis of Variance, a computed t-value of -1.20 was obtained, which was below the P-value, which is 0.233 at a 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted, and this means that there is no significant difference in the level of adversity quotient when grouped according to faculty designation.

In line with the mentioned result, Mulder (2014) makes the case that professional competence is a general, integrated, and internalized ability to realize sustainable performance effectively (including problem-solving, innovation, and creating transformation) in some professional domains. This argument is in line with the result that was previously mentioned. Professional competence in the educational context, particularly in teaching, is the mastery of a wide variety of instructional resources (Epstein and Hundert, 2002). Hence, in order to be able to do their jobs effectively in a constantly changing social and professional context, teachers must possess a set of general traits known as professional competence.

By recognizing the social circumstances surrounding instructional activities, professional activities can be sustained and self-development based on personality are supported (Orazbayeva, 2016).

Difference in the Level of Emotional Quotient of teachers when grouped in terms of Age

The table below shows the difference in the Emotional Quotient of catholic school teachers in terms of Age.

When it comes to the difference in emotional quotient when grouped according to age, 124 teachers aged 20-30 years old had a mean score of 4.07, 35 teachers aged 31-40 years old had a mean score of 4.09, 15 teachers aged 41-50 years old had a mean score of 3.93, 10 teachers aged 51-60 years had a mean score of 4.13, and 1 teacher aged above 60 years old had a mean score of 4.40.

Upon using the Analysis of Variance, a computed F-value of 0.57 was obtained, which is below the P-value, which is 0.684 at a 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted, meaning there is no significant difference in emotional quotient when grouped according to age.

Table 12. *Difference in Emotional Quotient of teachers when grouped according to Age*

Age	F	Mean
20-30 years old	124	4.07
31-40 years old	35	4.09
41-50 years old	15	3.93
51-60 years old	10	4.13
above 60 years old	1	4.40

Computed value (F) = 0.57
P-value = 0.684
Decision = Accept Ho
Interpretation = Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Yet, this contradicts other studies that revealed older people to have significantly greater emotional intelligence scores than young individuals across various measures. The positive relationship between age and emotional intelligence was thought to be explained by lifelong learning and acquired knowledge (Chapman & Hayslip, 2006).

Difference in the Level of Emotional Quotient of teachers when group in terms of Sex

The table below shows the difference in the Emotional Quotient of catholic school teachers in terms of Sex.

Table 13. *Difference in Emotional Quotient of teachers when grouped according to Sex*

Sex	f	Mean
Male	64	4.10
Female	121	4.05

Computed value (t) = 0.68
P-value = 0.497
Decision = Accept Ho
Interpretation = Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

Looking upon the difference in emotional quotient when grouped according to sex, 64 male teachers had a mean score of 4.10, while 121 female teachers had a mean score of 4.05.

Upon using Analysis of Variance, a computed t-value of 0.68 was obtained, which is higher than the P-value, which is 0.497 at a 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected, meaning there is no significant difference in emotional quotient when grouped according to sex.

This is in line with the findings of the study by Meshkat and Nejati (2017), which found that while there was no statistically significant difference between the sexes' overall emotional intelligence scores, there was a propensity for females to outperform males in the domains of emotional self-awareness, interpersonal relationships, self-esteem, and empathy.

Difference in the Level of Emotional Quotient of teachers when group in terms of Length of Service

The table below shows the difference in the Emotional Quotient of catholic school teachers in terms of Length of Service.

Table 14. *Difference in Emotional Quotient of teachers when grouped according to Length of Service*

Length of Service	f	Mean
5 years & below	129	4.08
6-10 years	28	4.07
11-15 years	14	4.10
16 years & above	14	3.99

Computed value (F) = 0.20
P-value = 0.898
Decision = Accept Ho
Interpretation = Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table shows that when it comes to the difference in emotional quotient when grouped according to the length of service, 129 teachers serving for five years & below had a mean score of 4.08, 28 teachers serving for 6-10 years had a mean score of 4.07, 14 teachers serving for 11-15 years and 16 years & above had a mean score of 4.10 and 3.99, respectively.

Using Analysis of Variance, the computed F-value of 0.20 was obtained, which was below the P-value, which was 0.898 at a 0.05 level of significance. The decision was to accept the null hypothesis, which means that there is no significant difference in the emotional quotient of teachers when grouped according to the length of service.

Nevertheless, there is now proof that mastering a few of the so-called "soft" abilities of emotional intelligence can not only help leaders

manage any team but also motivate team members to remain on for five years or longer—up to 70%, in fact (Kerr, 2023).

Difference in the Level of Emotional Quotient of teachers when group in terms of Employment Status

The table below shows the difference in the Emotional Quotient of catholic school teachers in terms of Employment Status.

Table 15. *Difference in Emotional Quotient of teachers when Grouped according to Employment Status*

<i>Employment Status</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Mean</i>
Permanent	104	4.05
Probationary	81	4.10

Computed value (t) = -0.81

P-value = 0.419

Decision=Accept Ho

Interpretation=Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table on the difference in emotional quotient when grouped according to employment status shows that 104 permanent teachers had a mean score of 4.05 and 81 probationary teachers had a mean score of 4.10.

A computed t-value of -0.81 was obtained upon using Analysis of Variance. This is below the P-value, which is 0.419 at a 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted, and this means that there is no significant difference in the level of teachers' emotional quotient when grouped according to employment status.

Emotional quotient also heavily relies on intrinsic motivation. Emotionally intelligent people are driven by factors other than material rewards like fame, money, recognition, and acclaim. Instead, they are passionate about achieving their own internal demands and objectives, which might include improving their employment situation. They look for internal rewards, enjoy the flow that comes from being completely present throughout an activity, and chase peak experiences (Orazbayeva, 2016).

Difference in the Level of Emotional Quotient of teachers when group in terms of Gross Monthly Income

The table below shows the difference in the Emotional Quotient of catholic school teachers in terms of Gross Monthly Income.

Table 16. *Difference in Emotional Quotient of teachers when grouped according to Gross Monthly Income*

<i>Gross Monthly Income</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean</i>
P10,000 & below	8	3.99
P10,001-P15,000	134	4.06
P15,001 & above	43	4.13

Computed value (F) = 0.52

P-value = 0.598

Decision=Accept Ho

Interpretation =Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

In identifying the emotional quotient difference in monthly income, eight teachers earning P10,000 & below had a mean score of 3.99, 134 teachers earning P10,001-P15,000 had a mean score of 4.06, and 43 teachers earning P15,001 & below had a mean score of 4.13.

A computed f-value of 0.52 was obtained upon using Analysis of Variance. This is below the P-value, which is 0.598 at a 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the decision was to accept the null hypothesis, which means there is no significant difference in teachers' emotional quotient level when grouped according to gross monthly income.

Emotionally intelligent people are driven by factors other than material rewards like fame, money, recognition, and acclaim. Instead, they are passionate about achieving their own internal demands and objectives, which might include improving their employment situation. They look for internal rewards, enjoy the flow that comes from being completely present throughout an activity, and chase peak experiences (Orazbayeva, 2016).

Difference in the Level of Emotional Quotient of teachers when group in terms of Faculty Designation

The table below shows the difference in the Emotional Quotient of catholic school teachers in terms of Faculty Designation.

Table 17. *Difference in Emotional Quotient of teachers when grouped according to Faculty Designation*

<i>Faculty Designation</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean</i>
Junior High School	109	4.06
Senior High School	76	4.08

Computed value (t) = -0.30

P-value = 0.762

Decision =Accept Ho

Interpretation =Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table shows that 109 Junior High School teachers had a mean score of 4.06 and 76 Senior High School teachers had a mean score of 4.08.

A computed t-value of -0.30 was obtained upon using Analysis of Variance. This is below the P-value which is 0.762 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the decision was to accept the null hypothesis and this means that there is no significant difference in the level of emotional quotient of teachers when grouped according to faculty designation.

Comparison between the means and Work Performance of Teachers when grouped in terms of Length of Service

Table below presents the comparison of the means and work performance of Teachers when grouped in terms of Length of Service.

Table 18. *Comparison of means and Work Performance in Terms of Length of Service*

<i>Comparison of Variables</i>	<i>Computed Value</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
5 years & below vs. 6-10 years	-0.19	0.294	Not significant
5 years & below vs. 11-15 years	-0.29	0.191	Not significant
5 years & below vs. 16 years & above	-0.42	0.021	Significant
6-10 years vs. 11-15 years	-0.10	0.935	Not significant
6-10 years vs. 16 years & above	-0.23	0.533	Not significant
11-15 years vs. 16 years & above	-0.13	0.914	Not significant

When comparing the means and work performance in terms of length of service, the table shows that five years & below versus 6-10 years obtained a computed value of -0.19 which was lower than the P-value which 0.294 and is interpreted as Not Significant. Comparing five years & below and 11-15 years, a computed value of -0.29 was obtained, which is lower than the P-value of 0.191 and is interpreted as Not Significant. However, comparing five years & below versus 16 years & above found Significant results as the computed value of -0.42 was obtained, which was below the P-value of 0.021.

Upon comparing 6-10 years and 11-15 years, a computed value of -0.10 was obtained, which was lower than the P-value of 0.935. This was interpreted as Not Significant. When it comes to 6-10 years versus 16 years & above, a computed value of -0.23 was obtained, which was lower than the P-value of 0.533. This was interpreted as Not Significant. Finally, comparing 11-15 years against 16 years & above, a computed value of -0.13 was obtained, which was below the P-value of 0.914. This result was interpreted as Not Significant.

This relates to a study by Ablaa and Isidro (2015), which indicated a negative correlation between job performance and years of service. This suggests that the number of years an employee has worked does not affect how well they do their job.

Moreover, individuals with longer tenure were better able to perform their jobs because they were more familiar with their job duties and may have obtained higher levels of professional accomplishment than less experienced workers, according to Ng and Sorensen (2008).

Difference in the Level of Work Performance of Teachers when grouped in terms of Age

The table below shows the difference in the Work Performance of catholic school teachers in terms of Age.

Table 19. *Difference in Work Performance of teachers when grouped according to Age*

<i>Age</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Mean</i>
20-30 years old	124	3.19
31-40 years old	35	3.28
41-50 years old	15	3.59
51-60 years old	10	3.35
above 60 years old	1	3.26

Computed value (F) = 2.55

P-value = 0.041

Decision = Reject Ho

Interpretation = Significant at 0.05 level of significance

Looking at the difference in work performance when grouped according to age, 124 teachers aged 20-30 years old had a mean score of 3.19, 35 teachers aged 31-40 years old had a mean score of 3.28, 15 teachers aged 41-50 years old had a mean score of 3.59, 10 teachers aged 51-60 years old had a mean score of 3.35, and 1 teacher aged above 60 years old had a mean score of 3.26.

Using the Analysis of Variance, a computed F-value of 2.55 was obtained, which is higher than the P-value, which is 0.041 at a 0.05 level of significance. The decision was to reject the null hypothesis. Hence, there is a significant difference in teachers' work performance when grouped according to age.

Age, consequently has no bearing on how well a job is done. According to Ablaa and Isidro (2008), age has no bearing on one's ability to execute a job. Smedley & Whitten also identified age as a potential factor in determining occupational effectiveness (2006).

Difference in the Level of Work Performance of Teachers when grouped in terms of Sex

The table below shows the difference in the Work Performance of catholic school teachers in terms of Sex.

Regarding the difference in the level of work performance when grouped according to sex, 64 male teachers had a mean score of 3.25, and 121 female teachers had a mean score of 3.24.

Table 20. *Difference in Work Performance when grouped according to Sex*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Mean</i>
Male	64	3.25
Female	121	3.24

Computed value (t) = 0.16
 P-value = 0.871
 Decision = Accept H_0
 Interpretation = Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The computed t-value was 0.16, which was lower than the P-value, which is 0.871 at a 0.05 level of significance. Hence, the null hypothesis was accepted, and this means that there is no significant difference in teachers' work performance when grouped according to sex.

Although male and female perceptions of sex differ, this has little impact on how well people perform at work. The research done in 2008 by Ablaa and Isidro supports the finding that gender had very little to no impact on job performance. They also concluded that men and women compete equally in the workplace.

Difference in the Level of Work Performance of Teachers when grouped in terms of Length of Service

The table below shows the difference in the Work Performance of catholic school teachers in terms of Length of Service.

Table 21. *Difference in Work Performance of teachers when grouped according to Length of Service*

<i>Length of Service</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>Mean</i>
5 years & below	129	3.16
6-10 years	28	3.35
11-15 years	14	3.46
16 years & above	14	3.59

Computed value (F) = 5.09
 P-value = 0.002
 Decision = Reject H_0
 Interpretation = Significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table shows that 129 teachers who are in the service for five years & below have a mean of 3.16 in work performance, 28 teachers who are in the service for 6-10 years have a mean score of 3.35, 14 teachers who are in the service for 11-15 years have a mean score of 3.46, and 14 teachers who are in the service for 16 years & above have a mean score of 3.59.

Using Analysis of Variance, a computed F-value of 5.09 was obtained, which is higher than the P-value of 0.002. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 level of significance. This means there is a significant difference in teachers' work performance when grouped according to the length of service.

Notwithstanding differences in how men and women view sex, this has little bearing on how well people perform at work. Gender had little to no influence on job performance, according to Ablaa and Isidro's 2008 study. They also concluded that there is no difference in how men and women compete at work.

Difference in the Level of Work Performance of Teachers when grouped in terms of Employment Status

The table below shows the difference in the Work Performance of catholic school teachers in terms of Employment Status.

Table 22. *Difference in Work Performance of teachers when grouped according to Employment Status*

<i>Employment Status</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Mean</i>
Permanent	104	3.41
Probationary	81	3.04

Computed value (t) = 5.36
 P-value = 0.000
 Decision = Reject H_0
 Interpretation = Significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table shows that when it comes to the difference between the level of work performance and employment status, 104 permanent teachers have a mean score of 3.41, and 81 teachers have a mean score of 3.04.

Upon using Analysis of Variance, a computed t-value of 5.36 was obtained, which is higher than the P-value of 0.000. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 level of significance. This means there is a significant difference in teachers' work performance levels when grouped in terms of employment status.

Employability is the collection of skills that increase their chances of choosing and obtaining a job where they will be happy and successful (Pool & Sewell, 2007). According to Hogan, Chamorro-Premuzic, and Kaiser (2013), an individual's high drive, willingness to work hard, and battling spirit, or what is referred to as the adversity quotient, are some factors that can affect employability. Businesses need their employees to have high adversity quotients in prosperous and challenging economic times.

Difference in the Level of Work Performance of Teachers when grouped in terms of Gross Monthly Income

The table below shows the difference in the Work Performance of catholic school teachers in terms of Gross Monthly Income.

Table 23. *Difference in Work Performance of teachers when grouped according to Gross Monthly Income*

Gross Monthly Income	F	Mean
P10,000 & below	8	3.02
P10,001-P15,000	134	3.15
P15,001 & above	43	3.58

Computed value (F) = 15.77
 P-value = 0.000
 Decision =Reject Ho
 Interpretation =Significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table shows that eight teachers earning P10,000 & below have a mean score of 3.02, 134 teachers earning P10,001 -P15,000 have a mean score of 3.15, and 43 teachers earning P15,001 & above have a mean score of 3.58.

Upon using Analysis of Variance, a computed f-value of 15.77 was obtained, significantly above the p-value of 0.000. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 level of significance. This means there is a significant difference in teachers' work performance when grouped according to gross monthly income.

Similar findings from other studies about the motivational power of money were reached (Bergmann & Scarpello, 2002). They confirmed that when employees execute their jobs successfully, getting this kind of reward is important and significantly impacts their performance.

Difference in the Level of Work Performance of Teachers when grouped in terms of Faculty Designation

Table 24 on the next page shows the difference in the Work Performance of catholic school teachers in terms of Faculty Designation.

Table 24. *Difference in Work Performance of teachers when grouped according to Faculty Designation*

Faculty Designation	F	Mean
Junior High School	109	3.23
Senior High School	76	3.27

Computed value (t) = -0.58
 P-value = 0.563
 Decision =Accept Ho
 Interpretation=Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table shows that 109 Junior High School Teachers have a mean score of 3.23 regarding work performance, and 76 Senior High School Teachers have a mean score of 3.27.

Using Analysis of Variance, a computed t-value of -0.58 was obtained, notably below the tabular value of 0.563. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected at a 0.05 level of significance. This means that the faculty designation of teachers does not necessarily relate to their job performances.

As such, professional competence in the educational context, having been designated in a faculty organization particularly in teaching, is the mastery of a wide variety of instructional resources (Epstein and Hundert, 2002). Hence, in order to be able to do their jobs effectively in a constantly changing social and professional context, teachers must possess a set of general traits known as professional competence.

Relationship between Adversity Quotient and Emotional Quotient of Teachers

Table below shows the relationship between Adversity and Emotional Quotients of Catholic Teachers in the Diocese of Kabankalan.

Table 25. *Relationship between the Adversity and Emotional Quotient of teachers*

Level of Adversity Quotient	Level of Emotional Quotient					Total
	Very high	High	Average	Low	Very low	
Very high	12	1	0	0	0	13
High	48	47	3	0	0	98
Moderate	13	50	10	0	0	73
Low	0	1	0	0	0	1
Very low	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	73	99	13	0	0	185

Computed value (G) = 0.69
 P-value= 0.000
 Decision =Reject Ho
 Interpretation=Significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table shows that 13 teachers had a Very High level of adversity quotient, 12 of which had a Very High level of emotional quotient,

and 1 had High emotional quotient. Also, there were 98 who got a High level of adversity quotient, 48 of which having Very High level of emotional quotient, 47 having High level of emotional quotient, and 3 having Average emotional quotient. The table also shows that there were 73 teacher who got Moderate level of adversity quotient, 13 of which having Very High level of emotional quotient, 50 having High emotional quotient, and 10 having Average emotional quotient. Consequently, only 1 had both low levels on adversity and emotional quotients.

Two significant fields—psychometrics and intelligence—were contributed by the research of (Effendi, Matore1 & Khairani, 2016) concerning the association between adversity and emotional quotient. The requirement that the data type be interval is one of the requirements for correlation analysis. To link AQ with other intelligences variables, the Rasch model significantly contributed to converting ordinal data (from the CTT) to interval data. In terms of intellect, it was conceptually hypothesized that AQ could boost IQ, EQ, and SQ quotients to produce top-tier human capital and the perfect personality.

Relationship between Adversity Quotient and Work Performance of Teachers

Table below shows the relationship between Adversity Quotients and Work Performance of Catholic Teachers in the Diocese of Kabankalan.

Table 26. Relationship between the Adversity Quotient and Work Performance of teachers

Level of Adversity Quotient	Level of Work Performance					Total
	Very Proficient	Proficient	Basic	Below Basic	Not Observed	
Very high	0	12	1	0	0	13
High	1	72	24	0	1	98
Moderate	0	53	19	1	0	73
Low	0	1	0	0	0	1
Very low	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	1	138	44	1	1	185

Computed value (G) = 0.12
 P-value = 0.423
 Decision =Accept Ho
 Interpretation= Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table shows that 12 teachers with Very High level of adversity quotient are Proficient in their work performance and only 1 with Very High level of adversity quotient has Basic work performance level. Out of 98 teachers with High adversity quotient level, 72 have Proficient work performance, 24 have Basic work performance level. Also, out of 73 teachers who have Moderate level of adversity quotient, 53 have Proficient work performance level, 19 have Basic work performance level, and 1 is Below Basic. Consequently, only 1 teacher has Low level of adversity quotient and is Proficient in work performance at the same time.

Using Pearson Product Moment Coefficient, a computed value of 0.12 was obtained below the p-value of 0.423. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted at 0.05 level of significance. This means that there is no relationship between adversity quotient and teachers' work performance and that a higher or lower AQ may not necessarily affect a person's job performance.

Lazaro's 2004 study, on the other hand, discovered that the demographic profile variables included in this study were not significantly related to the adversity quotient or the respondents' performance level. Nonetheless, the 360-degree feedback system revealed a strong relationship between performance and adversity quotient.

Relationship between Emotional Quotient and Work Performance of Teachers

Table below shows the relationship between Emotional Quotient and Work Performance of Catholic Teachers in the Diocese of Kabankalan.

Table 27. Relationship between the Emotional Quotient and Work Performance of teachers

Level of Emotional Quotient	Level of Work Performance					Total
	Very Proficient	Proficient	Basic	Below Basic	Not Observed	
Very high	0	59	14	0	0	73
High	1	71	25	1	1	99
Average	0	8	5	0	0	13
Low	0	0	0	0	0	0
Very low	0	0	0	0	0	0
Total	1	138	44	1	1	185

Computed value (G) = 0.24
 P-value = 0.110
 Decision =Accept Ho
 Interpretation =Not significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table shows that out of 73 teachers who have Very High level of emotional quotient, 59 have Proficient work performance level and 14 have Basic work performance level. Out of 99 teachers who have High emotional quotient level, 1 is Very Proficient in work performance, 71 are Proficient, 25 have Basic performance, and 1 is Below Basic. At the same time, out of 13 teachers who have

Average emotional quotient level, 8 are Proficient in work performance and 5 are Basic.

Using Pearson Product Moment Coefficient, a computed value of 0.24 was obtained which is below the P-value which is 0.110. Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means there is no significant relationship between the emotional quotient and teachers' work performance. The results imply that higher EQ does not necessarily result in better work performance.

Several experts believe that emotional intelligence is a key indicator in vocational and professional education. Students will have worthwhile lives if the educator employs emotional intelligence skillfully. To help their kids succeed academically, teachers must focus on their students' emotional literacy, and when they evaluate their emotional literacy, their emotional literacy will be clear (Zeidner, Matthews, & Roberts, 2011). Furthermore, emotionally intelligent teachers demonstrate compassion for their students and foster a positive emotional climate in the classroom, improving the learning environment for children and increasing teachers' ability to ensure an academic achievement. Emotional intelligence has been linked to teachers' comfort level, sense of self-efficacy, enjoyment at work, and improved social interactions with students. As a result, emotional intelligence directly impacts how children are taught and learn (Jennings & Greenberg, 2009).

Conclusions

The following are the conclusions established based on the results derived.

Most of the teachers are female, young in age, new in the service yet mostly are permanent, with an income of more than 10, 000 and designated to junior high school.

Catholic School Teachers have high adversity quotients.

Catholic School Teachers have high emotional quotients.

Catholic School Teachers have proficient work performance.

Regardless of age, sex, length of service employment status, gross monthly income and faculty designation the adversity quotient of teachers does not vary.

When grouped according to age, sex, length of service employment status, gross monthly income and faculty designation the emotional quotient of teachers does not vary at all.

The work performance of teachers shows a significant difference in terms of age, length of service and gross monthly income and employment status and is no significant difference in terms of sex and faculty designation.

The adversity and emotional quotients of teachers show a significant relationship.

The relationship of adversity quotient and work performance shows no significance.

The relationship of emotional quotient and work performance shows no significance.

Based on the results and conclusions formulated the following recommendations are advanced by the researchers:

Age, Permanency and employment status should be given emportance by the school's administrators and consider the length of service and monthly income of the teachers for a productive work performance.

Enhancement programs such as training and seminar workshop on maintaining the adversity quotient may be done to help teachers not only realize for themselves but also to apply it among their learners.

Mental health activities can be given to teachers to maintain the emotional quotient and their level of emotions may be recognized for immediate emotional response on emerging problems.

School Heads and principals may give recognition of the individuality and diversity of the skills and capacities of teachers must be noted in the implementation of school - based programs as well as in the conduct trainings and seminars to facilitate equal development of their performances.

The Diocese of Kabankalan Commission on Education can adopt the same work performance assessment tool in evaluating the faculty of every school under the diocese for the uniformity of assessment.

A developmental program in support of adversity and emotional quotient may be done schools by school heads in recognition of the fact that an emotionally intelligent teacher is the first step to an emotionally intelligent classroom.

Relevant studies may also be encouraged using the same concepts with a wider scope including more variables to deeply determine the performance of teachers, hence, improving them to be better and efficient in school.

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